

O'ZBEK VA INGLIZ TILLARIDA OZIQ-OVQAT KONSEPTUAL MAYDONI KONSEPTUAL IBORALARINING LINGVOMADANIY TADQIQI

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Abstrakt: Ushbu maqolada turli tillarda ifodalanadigan oziq-ovqat konseptual iboralari, iboralar tahlili, ularning madaniy ahamiyati, ularning o'ziga xos xususiyatlari tilning shakllanishida ularning o'rni yoritib berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: iboralar, oziq-ovqat konseptini ifodalovchi iboralar, frazeologik birikmalar.

Turli tillarda idiomalar o'ziga xos xususiyatlarga ega hisoblanadi. Ular nafaqat tilni boyitadi, unga estetik zavq beradi, oddiylikdan ko'ra tasviriy ifodalar bilan ifodalash orqali nutni chiroyli qiladi.

Apple of his eye - A favorite person of someone.

She was the apple of her father's eye and he always went out of his way to get her what she wanted

Apple of his eye-ko'zining oqu qorasi. Idiomalarda ma'no ko'chishi har xil usullarda kuzatiladi, qisman, butunlay, ya'ni so'z ma'nosi idiomaga ta'sir qiladigan, yoki umuman o'z ma'nosini yo'qotgan bo'lishi mumkin. Bunda apple so'zi umuman o'z ma'nosini yo'qotgan hisoblanadi.

Buy a lemon - Buy something worthless.

She bought a lemon and always had problems with the car.

Limon sotib olish-ma'nosi umuman biz kutmagan holda, ma'noda keladi, ya'ni arzimaydigan narsa sotib olish, pulini behuda sarflash. Bu iborada limon so'zi o'z ma'nosini yo'qotgan va yangi ko'chma ma'no ifdalagan.

Compare apples and oranges - To compare things that are very different.

You can't compare a race car with a skateboard, that's like comparing apples to oranges

Olma va apelsinlarni taqqoslash-turli, o'xshash bo'lmagan narsalarni taqqoslash. Ma'no qisman saqlangan bo'lishi mumkin, lekin har xil narsalarni taqqoslash, ularning umuman bitta turdan emasligini, ularni taqqoslab bo'lmasligini bildiradi.

Cool as a cucumber -To remain calm and collected.

She was as cool as a cucumber in the interview and impressed everyone

Bodringdek sovuq yoki vazmin. Boshqa tillarda bu o'xshatish tubdan farq qiladi, lekin ingliz tilida bodringga o'xshatiladi. Bosiq, vazmin inson bodring kabi vazmin deb iborada ifodalanadi.

Life is a bowl of cherries - Life is good and pleasant.

He tried to convince her that life of a bowl of cherries in his new town

Hayot bu 1 kosa gilos. Bu ibora insonda mavhum tushuncha hosil qiladi. Ya'ni, bu iborani 1-marta o'qigan inson iboradan ma'no topolmasligi mumkin.

Hayot qiziqarli va yoqimli. Hayot qisqa va tez o'tadi, shuning uchun undan foydalanib qolish kerak, uni yaxshi o'tkazish kerak kabi ma'nolarni tushunish mumkin.

Top banana - Leader or boss.

She was the top banana in her class and everyone looked up to her

Top banan-ya'ni top-yuqori banan. Bu iborada ham ma'noning butunlay yo'qolishini kuzatishimiz, bunga guvoh bo'lishimiz mumkin. Bu ibora lider, yo'lboshchi, eng ilg'or insonga nisbatan ishlatiladi. U sinfida eng ilg'or bo'lgani uchun hamma uni hurmat qiladi.

Xulosa.

Har bir tildagi idiomalar va frazalar o'ziga xos xususiyatlarga ega hisoblanadi va ularning ma'nolari boshqa tillarda boshqa iboralar bilan ifodalanishini kuzatishimiz mumkin. Yoki bunday tushuncha umuman boshqa bir tilde mavjuda bo'lmasligi mumkin. Bu jamiyat an'anasi va qadriyatlariga bog'liqdir. Millatning madaniy va milliy tushunchalari, o'ziga xos qadriyatlari bu yerda juda muhim o'rin tutadi. Bu iboralardagi tag va asl ma'no, ko'chma ma'nolar millatning o'ziga xos qadriyat va tushunchalariga xos tarzda ifodalanadi.

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